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SOME ISSUES OF DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS OF STUDENTS IN THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT: The article illustrates some issues of teaching in the Credit module system and its advantages and disadvantages in teaching students at Universities in the Uzbekistan. Moreover, the article shows some methods of developing speaking skills

KEY WORDS: credit module system, speaking skills, advantages and disadvantages of using credit module system in Teaching in Uzbekistan

INTRODUCTION

We can say that studying the concept of language and speech and conducting scientific research about the differences and similarities between them is not one of the new issues today. Because language and speech is a matter related to people themselves. Each nation has its own language, which is expressed through speech. Through language, it is possible to show how rich the culture of each nation and people is. For these reasons, the issue of language teaching is one of the most pressing issues. However, in today's fast-paced environment of rapidly changing educational systems, it can be seen that there are several issues that need to be explored. The credit module system was a new stage of the educational process for our state educational standards. Therefore, it is necessary to recognize that this educational system has a direct impact on the educational process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Several materials and internet sites have been used to write this little research article in order to illustrate some issues of teaching speaking in credit module system (as an example of teaching English). It is known that online language teaching is very difficult, because practical lessons play an important role in it, and independent learning is a very difficult issue. The introduction of the measure of credit accumulation not only gave the student great freedom, but also provided an opportunity to independently plan the academic process in order to become a competitive specialist in the field of his choice in the future. At the same time, it also led to improvements in the assessment system and educational technology.

Based on the decision of the Court of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2020 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of educational processes in higher education institutions" "Death in higher education institutions regulation on the procedure for introducing the credit-module system into the educational process" was approved. In this Regulation, the basic concepts of the credit-module system have been given. According to him:

GPA (Grade Point Average) is the average value of the student's points for the program, which is calculated using the following formula:

$$GPA = \frac{K_1U_1 + K_2U_2 + K_3U_3 \dots + K_nU_n}{K_1 + K_2 + K_3 \dots + K_n}$$
 : is equal to $K_1 + K_2 + K_3 \dots + K_n$.

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It is as the followings:

K — amount of credits allocated to each subject/module;

U is the student's grade for each subject/module;

A credit is a unit of measurement of the educational load mastered by a student in a specific subject according to the results of education. Loans can be expressed in whole, fractional numbers according to the rule;

Accumulation of credit - accumulation of credit units provided as a result of mastering educational elements and achieving other achievements;

A student's personal educational trajectory is a direction (route) chosen by the student and which gives him the opportunity to accumulate knowledge in a sequence and acquire the desired set of competencies.

Study load - all types of educational activities by the student - lecture, practical training, seminar, laboratory work, course project (work), practice and independent work are necessary to achieve the expected learning results and the volume of hours.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSIONS

Credit system learning systems can be very effective in developing learning processes to provide flexible and adaptive learning to students. These systems provide students with the opportunity to customize their own learning based on evolving techniques and the latest information. Methods of developing speaking skills can be as follows:

Creative Lessons and Practical Exercises: Students can develop their speaking skills by providing creative lessons and practical exercises in credit-module systems. Creative activities give students the opportunity to solve problems, express valid ideas, and repeat ideas.

Interactive Learning Tools: Students develop their speaking skills through lectures, online tutorials, video lessons, and interactive tutorials. These tools allow students to express themselves and think.

Group Work and Discussion: Encouraging students to think with each other through group work and discussion methods can be very effective in developing their negotiation and speaking skills.

Portfolios and Presentations: Prepare portfolios and organize presentations to help students improve their speaking skills. This method is useful for students to express themselves, process information and communicate their ideas to others.

Practical Projects and Accountability: Students develop their speaking skills by encouraging them to participate in real-life tools, working on projects, rehearsing new ideas and presenting themselves to others.

Management and Monitoring: Credit module systems create new opportunities for students to manage and monitor themselves. This helps to develop personal learning according to the interests and requirements of each of the students.

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Credit-module systems create opportunities for students to improve their learning and are very effective in developing their speaking skills. These systems allow students to develop themselves and express themselves.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I would like to mention some advantages and disadvantages of the credit module system. A unique feature of the credit module system is that students learn independent learning and independent development. One of the key advantages is flexibility. The credit module system allows students to choose courses according to their interests, pace of learning, and individual capabilities. They can also select courses from different disciplines, which provides a more well-rounded education.

Moreover, students have the opportunity to learn at their own pace. They can progress through modules at a speed that suits their learning style and understanding, allowing for better comprehension and retention of knowledge. As well as Students can tailor their coursework to align with their career goals or specific areas of interest, fostering a sense of ownership in their education. The credit system often allows for easier credit transfer between institutions, both nationally and internationally. This flexibility can be beneficial for students who might need to change schools or pursue study abroad opportunities. At last, not least, the modular structure encourages skill enhancement. Students can focus on specific skills or subjects they find challenging, dedicating more time and effort to improve in those areas.

Nevertheless, there are still some disadvantages in this learning system which are waiting being solved, they are Implementing and managing the credit system requires complex administrative processes. The coordination of various modules, credit evaluation, and transfer can be challenging for educational institutions. As students have the freedom to choose their courses, there's a risk of fragmented knowledge. Some may opt for courses that interest them but might not necessarily contribute to a holistic education. The next issue is that the flexibility can also lead to an increased workload and stress for students who take on too many credits simultaneously or struggle with managing their time effectively. The Credit Module System offers significant advantages in terms of flexibility and personalized learning experiences. However, its effective implementation requires careful planning, guidance, and oversight to mitigate potential drawbacks and ensure a balanced and quality education for students.

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